

Modeling and Analysis of a Perishable Inventory System with Retrial Customers and Server Breakdown

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Abstract

This study examines an inventory system combined with a service facility that is affected by server breakdowns and product perishability. When the server is busy, incoming customers join an infinite-capacity orbit and attempt service again later instead of exiting the system. Each customer who receives service leaves with one unit of inventory, and stock is managed using an (s, S) replenishment policy. Service interruptions may occur due to server failures; if a breakdown happens while the server is busy, the system continues functioning at a lower service rate. Following a random repair duration, the server returns to operation in the idle state. Moreover, stored items deteriorate over time. The steady-state joint probability distribution of the number of customers in orbit, the inventory level, and the server condition is derived using probabilistic methods. Several performance metrics are obtained, and a detailed cost function is developed. Numerical studies are conducted to demonstrate the analytical findings and to analyze the impact of key system parameters. Finally, numerical examples are provided to illustrate the results.

Keywords and phrases: (s, S) Policy; Perishable Inventory; Service Facility; Server Breakdown;

1 INTRODUCTION

This research examines a perishable inventory system integrated with a service facility that is subject to working breakdowns and retrial customer behavior. In real-life situations, inventory items such as food products, medicines, and other consumables have a limited lifetime, and their perishable plays a significant role in determining system performance. At the same time, service facilities are often exposed to interruptions and reduced efficiency due to breakdowns, making the analysis of such systems more realistic and practically relevant. This research examines a perishable inventory system integrated with a service facility that is prone to occasional server breakdowns.[1] Reshmi and Jose analyzed a queueing-inventory system with perishable items and retrial customers. [2] Ke in examined the $M/G/1$ system under different operational policies such as startup, shutdown, and breakdowns, thereby extending classical queueing models to more realistic conditions. Krishnamoorthy et al. in [3] presented a survey of inventory models with positive service time, contributing to the understanding of combined queueing-inventory systems. Neuts [4] in the book Matrix geometric solution in stochastic models explained detail about an algorithmic approach. White and Christie in [5] were among the first to study queueing systems with preemptive priority and breakdowns, demonstrating how server interruptions affect system performance. Singh and Prasher in [6] developed a production inventory model with flexible manufacturing,

random machine breakdowns, and stochastic repair time, thereby incorporating practical manufacturing considerations into theoretical models. Further, Schwarz et al. in [7] described an M/M/1 queueing system integrated with inventory, providing a framework for analyzing the interaction between customer service and stock levels. Prasanna Lakshmi et al. in [8] developed a queueing inventory system with server working breakdowns, which combines the effects of inventory depletion and server unreliability in a unified model. From the above literature, it is evident that considerable work has been carried out in the areas of queueing systems, inventory models, and their integration under various realistic assumptions such as breakdowns, retrial customers, and stochastic repair times. However, the study of perishable inventory systems combined with service facilities and working breakdowns still requires further exploration. This approach allows for a detailed analysis of system performance under complex and uncertain conditions. The results of this study can be applied to various real-life systems such as healthcare, manufacturing, and supply chain management, where efficient inventory control and service reliability are essential.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

We consider a continuous review inventory system with a single server, where demand items are delivered after a random service time. The inventory has a maximum capacity of S . Customer arrivals follow a Poisson process with rate α . If the server is busy, the arriving customers enter an orbit, which has infinite capacity and excludes the customer currently being served. Service is provided on a First-Come, First-Served (FCFS) basis, and the service time follows an exponential distribution with rate γ_1 . Items in the inventory are subject to perishability, meaning they may spoil over time. The perishability follows an exponential distribution with parameter β . An (s, S) inventory policy is implemented with a positive lead time. When the inventory level falls to a predetermined reorder point s , an order of size $Q (= S - s > s + 1)$ is placed. The ordered items are received after a random lead time, which is exponentially distributed with parameter ρ . The server is also prone to breakdown during service, with the time until failure following an exponential distribution with parameter ν . The server goes to working under breakdown to follow an exponential rate γ_2 and $\gamma_1 > \gamma_2$. Once the server breaks down, it undergoes a repair process, with repair times following an exponential distribution with parameter σ . When the server becomes idle, retrial customers may reattempt to enter into the service point. The time between retrial attempts is exponentially distributed with parameter θ . All stochastic components in the model including inter-arrival times, service times, lead times, repair times, and retrial times are assumed to be mutually independent.

Let $N(t)$ be a customer in the orbit at time t , $L(t)$ be on hand inventory level at time t , and $Y(t)$ be the status of the server at time t .

$$Y(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{the server is idle} \\ 1, & \text{the server is busy} \\ 2, & \text{the server is in under under breakdown} \\ 3, & \text{the server is in under working breakdown.} \end{cases}$$

From the assumption made on the input and output processes, it can be show that the stochastic process $\{(N(t), L(t), Y(t)), t \geq 0\}$ is a continuous time Markov chain with state space.

$$\langle (n, l, y) \rangle = \begin{cases} (n, 0, y), & n \geq 0; \quad y = 0, 2; \\ (n, l, y), & n \geq 0; \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad y = 0, 1, 2, 3; \end{cases}$$

The ordering of the above states space ($\ll 0 \gg, \ll 1 \gg, \ll 2 \gg, \dots$), the infinitesimal generator T (block matrix) can be conveniently written in a block partitioned matrix as shown below.

$$T = \begin{matrix} & \ll 0 \gg & \ll 1 \gg & \ll 2 \gg & \ll 3 \gg & \ll 4 \gg \\ \begin{matrix} \ll 0 \gg \\ \ll 1 \gg \\ \ll 2 \gg \\ \ll 3 \gg \\ \vdots \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} P_1 & P_0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ P_2 & P_3 & P_0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & P_2 & P_3 & P_0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & P_2 & P_3 & P_0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

where,

$$[P_0]_{l'l} = \begin{cases} A_0, & l=l, \quad l=0; \\ A_1, & l=l, \quad l=1,2,\dots,S; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}, \quad A_0 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 2 \\ 2 & \alpha \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{pmatrix}, \quad A_1 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$[P_1]_{l'l} = \begin{cases} B_0, & l' = Q, \quad l = 0; \\ B_1, & l' = Q + 1, \quad l = 1,2,\dots,S; \\ B_2, & l' = l - 1, \quad l = 1; \\ B_3, & l' = l - 1, \quad l = 2,\dots,S; \\ B_4, & l' = l, \quad l = 0; \\ B_5, & l' = l, \quad l = 1,\dots,S; \\ B_6, & l' = l, \quad l = s + 1,\dots,S; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}, \quad B_0 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 2 \\ 2 & \rho \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} \rho & 0 \\ 0 & \rho \end{pmatrix},$$

$$B_1 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & \rho & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & \rho & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & \rho \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \rho \end{pmatrix}, \quad B_2 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 0 \\ 2 & \beta \\ 3 & 0 \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} \beta \\ (\beta + \gamma_1) \\ 0 \\ (\beta + \gamma_2) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$B_3 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & \beta & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \gamma_1 & \beta & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & \beta \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & \gamma_2 \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \beta \end{pmatrix}, \quad B_4 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 2 & -(\rho + \alpha) \\ 0 & \sigma \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -(\sigma + \alpha + \rho) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$B_5 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -(\beta + \alpha + \rho) & \alpha & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_1 + \rho + \alpha + \nu) & \nu \\ 2 & \sigma & 0 & -(\beta + \sigma + \alpha + \rho) \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_2 + \rho + \alpha) \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \alpha \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix},$$

$$B_6 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -(\beta + \alpha) & \alpha & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_1 + \alpha + \nu) & \nu \\ 2 & \sigma & 0 & -(\beta + \sigma + \alpha) \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_2 + \alpha) \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \alpha \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix},$$

$$[P_2]_{l'l} = \begin{cases} C_0, & l' = l, \quad l = 1,2,\dots,S; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}, \quad C_0 = \begin{matrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & \theta & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 0 & \theta \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$[P_3]_{ll'} = \begin{cases} B_0, & l' = Q, & l = 0; \\ B_1, & l' = Q + 1, & l = 1, 2, \dots, s; \\ B_2, & l' = l - 1, & l = 1; \\ B_3, & l' = l - 1, & l = 2, \dots, S; \\ B_4, & l' = l, & l = 0 \\ D_0, & l' = l, & l = 1, 2, \dots, s; \\ D_1, & l' = l, & l = s + 1, \dots, S; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$$D_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & -(\beta + \alpha + \rho + \theta) & \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_1 + \rho + \alpha + v) & v & 0 \\ 3 & \sigma & 0 & -(\beta + \sigma + \rho + \theta + \alpha) & \alpha \\ & 0 & 0 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_2 + \rho + \alpha) \end{pmatrix},$$

$$D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & -(\beta + \alpha + \theta) & \alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_1 + \alpha + v) & v & 0 \\ 3 & \sigma & 0 & -(\beta + \sigma + \theta + \alpha) & \alpha \\ & 0 & 0 & 0 & -(\beta + \gamma_2 + \alpha) \end{pmatrix},$$

2.1 Stability Analysis

The stability condition of the process under study can be obtained through a smaller sized matrix $F = P_2 + P_3 + P_0$ is rate matrix of a finite state Markov process. We have

$$[F]_{ij} = \begin{cases} G_1, & j = i, & i = 0; \\ G_2, & j = i, & i = 1, 2, \dots, s; \\ G_3, & j = i, & i = s + 1, \dots, S; \\ B_0, & j = Q, & i = 0; \\ B_1, & j = Q + 1, \dots, S, & i = 1, 2, \dots, s; \\ B_2, & j = i - 1, & i = 1; \\ B_3, & j = i - 1, & i = 2, \dots, S; \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

where, $G_1 = A_0 + B_4$, $G_2 = A_1 + B_5 + C_0 + D_0$; $G_3 = A_1 + B_6 + C_0 + D_1$. Since this process is irreducible, its steady state probability distribution $\Pi = (\pi^{(0)}, \pi^{(1)}, \pi^{(2)}, \dots, \pi^{(s)})$ exists and satisfies

$$\Pi F = 0 \text{ and} \tag{1}$$

$$\Pi e = 1 \tag{2}$$

From the above two equations, we get the following set of equations

$$\pi^{(i)} G_1 + \pi^{(i+1)} B_2 = 0 \quad i = 0,$$

$$\pi^{(i)} G_2 + \pi^{(i+1)} B_3 = 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, s,$$

$$\pi^{(i)} G_3 + \pi^{(i+1)} B_3 = 0 \quad i = s + 1, \dots, Q - 1,$$

$$\pi^{(i)} G_3 + \pi^{(i+1)} B_3 + \pi^{(j)} B_0 = 0 \quad i = Q, j = 0$$

$$\pi^{(i)} G_3 + \pi^{(i+1)} B_3 + \pi^{(j)} B_1 = 0 \quad i = Q+1, \dots, S - 1, j = 1, 2, \dots, s - 1$$

$$\pi^{(i)}G_3 + \pi^{(j)}B_1 = 0 \quad i = S, j = s,$$

Now we can find the vector Π by using the above set of equations. Since F is a tri-diagonal block matrix, so we can use the algorithm given by Gaver algorithm to solve these system of equations.

The stability condition of the system under study is given by

$$\alpha\pi^{(0)}e + \alpha(\pi^{<1,1>} + \pi^{<1,3>}) < \theta(\pi^{<1,0>} + \pi^{<1,2>}), \text{ where } 1 = 1, 2, \dots, S \quad (3)$$

Proof: The lemma follows from the well-known results of Neuts (4) the positive recurrence of T , we have

$$\Pi P_0 e < \Pi P_2 e \quad (4)$$

and by exploiting the structure of the matrices P_0, P_2, Π , we get stability condition.

2.2 Steady State Analysis

It can be seen from the irreducible structure of the rate matrix T and from the lemma 1 that the continuous time discrete state space Markov chain $\{(N(t), L(t), Y(t)), t \geq 0\}$ is regular. Hence the limiting distribution ϕ exists and is independent of the initial state. That is $\phi = (\phi^{(0)}, \phi^{(1)}, \dots)$ satisfies

$$\Pi T = 0, \Pi e = 1 \quad (5)$$

Theorem: 1 When the stability condition holds good, the steady-state probability vector ϕ is given by

$$\phi^{(i)} = \phi^{(0)} R^i, i = 1, 2, \dots \quad (6)$$

where the matrix R satisfy the matrix quadratic equation

$$R^2 P_2 + R P_3 + P_0 = 0 \quad (7)$$

and the vector $\phi^{(0)}$ is obtained by solving

$$\phi^{(0)} (P_1 + R P_0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

subject to the normalizing condition

$$\phi^{(0)} (I - R)^{-1} e = 1 \quad (9)$$

The first equation of (5) yields

$$\phi^{(0)} P_1 + \phi^{(1)} P_2 = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\phi^{(i-1)} P_0 + \phi^{(i)} P_3 + \phi^{(i+1)} P_2 = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots \quad (11)$$

Proof The theorem follows from the well-known result on matrix-geometric methods Neuts [4]

3. SYSTEM PERFORMANCE MEASURES

In this section, we derive some important system performance measures in the steady performance measures in the steady state. Using them, we construct a long run total expected cost function.

3.1 Expected Inventory Level

$$\chi_I = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^S l \phi^{(n,l)} e$$

3.2 Expected Number of Customers in the Orbit

$$\chi_N = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \phi^{(n)} e$$

3.3 Expected Reorder Rate

$$\chi_{RE} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \gamma_1 \phi^{(n,s+1,1)} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \gamma_2 \phi^{(n,s+1,3)} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{y=0}^3 \beta \phi^{(n,s+1,y)}$$

3.4 Expected Repair Rate

$$\chi_R = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sigma \phi^{(n,l,2)}$$

3.5 Expected Perishable Rate

$$\chi_{PR} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^S \beta \phi^{(n,l)} e$$

3.6 Expected Breakdown Rate

$$\chi_B = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^S v \phi^{(n,l,1)}$$

3.7 Expected Working Breakdown Rate

$$\chi_W = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^S \gamma_2 \phi^{(n,l,3)} e$$

4 TOTAL EXPECTED COST RATE

The long-run total expected cost rate for this model is defined to be

$$TC(s, S) = c_h \chi_I + c_o \chi_N + c_s \chi_{RE} + c_r \chi_R + c_{pr} \chi_{PR} + c_b \chi_B + c_w \chi_W \quad \text{where,}$$

c_h : The inventory carrying cost per unit item per unit time

c_s : Setup cost rate

c_o : Waiting cost of a customer in the orbit per unit time

c_r : Server service cost per repair per unit time

c_{pr} : Perishable cost per unit time

c_b : Cost of server breakdown per unit time

c_w : Cost of working under server breakdown per unit time

5 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The function $TC(s, S)$ appears to be convex based on extensive numerical experimentation optimal values of the total cost rate, denoted as TC^* , s^* and S^* , are obtained through a simple numerical search process. A typical three-dimensional plot of the expected total cost function is presented in Figure 1.

The optimal cost value $TC^* = 2.9822$ is achieved at $(s^*, S^*) = (3, 12)$, for the fixed parameter values $\alpha = 1.56$; $\gamma_1 = 2.21$; $r = 0.7$; $\rho = 1.73$; $\gamma_2 = 1.85$; $\sigma = 2.5$; $\theta = 2.39$; $\beta = 0.9$; $\vartheta = 0.6$; $c_h = 0.1$; $c_s = 10$; $c_o = 1.5$; $c_r = 2.3$; $c_{pr} = 0.5$; $c_b = 0.2$; $c_w = 0.8$;

Figure1: A typical three-dimensional plot illustrating the convexity of the total expected cost rate

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